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Solar Heat for Industrial Processes (SHIP)

Danilo Alvesd's photograph (Unsplash)

H2020: ASTEP Project

BARBERO R.¹, MONTES M.J.¹, ABBAS R.² ENRIQUEZ J.³, ROVIRA, A¹

¹Research Group: Thermal Systems and Renewable Energies (Grupo de Investigación en Sistemas Térmicos y Energías Renovables (GISTER)). Thermal Engineering department of the ETSII (Industrial Engineering School) UNED

² ETSII UPM

³ ANALISIS-DSC

The GISTER coordinates this European project, whit 9 countries involved. Two large-scale prototypes will be designed and installed, which will use solar energy as the primary source for the selected industrial processes. The project starts from the rotating solar collector, SunDial (Spanish patent: UPM + UNED), for which technological solutions will be proposed to overcome the limitations of current systems.

ASTEP¹ (Application of Solar Thermal Energy to Processes) is categorized within the European H2020² research projects focused on renewable heat and cooling generation and energy supply with low cost and emissions.

The project was awarded to a consortium coordinated by Antonio Rovira, a full professor of the ETSII of UNED. The consortium is formed by 16 partners from 9 European countries (Spain, United Kingdom, Cyprus, Italy, Greece, Romania, France, Poland and Ireland). They will combine their knowledge and expertise in research and business.

The project started on May the 1st of 2020 and, during the next four years, the solar collector SunDial (Fig. 1) will be adapted to supply a

significant percentage of the heating and cooling demand for the process industry. It will be done for temperatures and latitudes where the current designs have failed.

Fig 1. SunDial solar collector

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web del Proyecto de investigación

Application of Solar Thermal Energy to Processes (ASTEP) will create a new innovative Solar Heating for Industrial Processes (SHIP) concept focused on overcoming the current limitations of these systems. SHIP is becoming increasingly relevant as one of the ways to meet the high thermal energy demand required for industry.

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Web H2020

Horizon 2020 is the biggest EU Research and Innovation program ever with nearly €80 billion of funding available over 7 years (2014 to 2020) – in addition to the private investment that this money will attract. It promises more breakthroughs, discoveries and world-firsts by taking great ideas from the lab to the market.

The SunDial is the result of four Spanish patents [2-5] and two international ones that belong to UPM and UNED [6-7].

The SunDial is a rotatory Fresnel collector that consists of a horizontal platform that rotates around a vertical axis, with a Fresnel type linear concentrator on top of the primary concentrating mirrors. These mirrors are curved following an arc of a circle and are located in parallel with the receiver, directing the radiation towards its whole length (fig. 1).

Similarly, these mirrors can be fixed or not, rotating around their longitudinal axis to obtain a two-axis solar tracking and improving the average solar optical performance. These type of concentrators suffers from high radiation losses at the end of the receiver because of their low length. In order to reduce these end losses, the receiver is enlarged and some other solutions are proposed: such as the introduction of a mirror that would reflect the rays that, on the contrary, would not hit on the receiver (fig. 1), modifying the slope of the platform (fig. 2).

Fig 2. Effect of the slope of the mirrors

They are technical solutions that will be analysed and optimized during the project development to provide a system adapted for the generation of solar heat at medium temperatures for industrial processes located at latitudes where it is not currently done.

Specifically, the project proposes the installation of two large prototypes in industrial environments according to the established

objective of reaching TRL 5 (Technology Readiness Level):

- Pasteurization process, generating heat at 175°C in a dairy factory located in Greece (latitude: 37.93 N).
- Preheating process over 220 °C in a steel factory for metallic tubes processing in Romania (latitude: 47.1 N).

Currently, there are 111 SHIP plants operating in Europe, according to the IEA database, task 49 [8]. 17 of them work with temperatures higher than 150 °C, and only in 6 European countries.

The challenge is to supply heat above this temperature and in higher latitudes, using a Fresnel concentrator, which is a technology with high potential for cost reduction. For the Romanian test site, a two-axis-tracking SunDial will be selected in order to reach this objective.

This collector will be integrated with a thermal energy storage system based on PCM (Phase change materials) and they will be managed by a control system to keep the continuous operation for the whole day. This objective will be reached for some of the summer days.

If the objectives are quantified, the project seeks to meet the following challenges:

- Reach up to 135 kWh of thermal production per day and 25 MWh of annual thermal production in each case study.
- Avoid the emission of 5.7 t of CO₂ and 5 kg of NO_x into the atmosphere.

Save the consumption of 2 t of fossil gas.

In addition, the ASTEP system will allow reaching other important objectives for the project:

- Reduce maintenance requirements, which in the Greek case is guaranteed because the mirrors will be fixed.

- Avoid introducing changes in current industrial processes.

These objectives are intended to be achieved through the development of some tasks in which the UNED will be intensively involved, in collaboration with the other partners of the ASTEP project:

- Carrying out thermo-fluid-mechanical simulations that allow characterizing the operation of the different elements (figs. 3, 5 and 7).
- Development of in-home tools to simulate its steady and transient behaviour (fig. 4).
- Laboratory tests for the cases of the storage system and, selection and assembly of the mirrors.
- Carrying out tests of the prototypes within the facilities of the Polytechnic University of Madrid (UPM) and the Polytechnic University of Cartagena (UPCT), which will allow the consortium researchers access to an important database to improve their developments.

THERMAL STORAGE SYSTEM

Figure 3 shows the evolution of the solid fusion process during the loading stage, obtained through computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations obtained by the company ANALISIS-DSC using the ANSYS-CFX code.

The Heat Transfer Fluid (HTF) flows through a pipe surrounded by fins. The heat is transferred to the PCM, starting the fusion close to the walls of the tube and these fins, and it is extending to the bulk as its load progress.

Phase change processes present a complex phenomenology and the models that are used to characterize them are part of the state of the art in this field. Therefore, it will be necessary to carry out a validation of the results through laboratory tests. The Politechnika Wroclawska University in Poland will be in charge of carrying out these experiments.

Fig 3. Time history of the fluid volume fraction in the storage system. Simulation done by the company ANALISIS-DSC

Once the CFD model has been validated, several transitory simulations of a basic unit of the storage system will be carried out, which will allow the development of analytical models, focused on characterizing the energy that can be stored at each moment and the loading and unloading times.

Furthermore, the analytical model will be integrated into a dynamic tool focused on analysing its coupling with the solar collector and the process.

SOLAR COLLECTOR

One of the key points of the project is the characterization of the collector, which will be carried out through the development of specific tools by the UPM and the UNED, based on developments of both universities.

As a first step, it is necessary to know the concentration of solar rays on the receiver (fig. 4), which will be obtained based on a ray-tracing tool developed at UPM.

Fig 4. Assessment of the optical performance of the SunDial

This tool allows evaluating the solar concentration on the receiver for different collector configurations, taking into account both the longitudinal and transverse angles. The goal will be to obtain a system with optimal behaviour from the optical point of view, by sizing parameters such as the number, width and length of mirrors, among other parameters.

In order to obtain a good concentration of the solar rays, the mirrors will be curved. For this reason, it is necessary to test whether the mirrors withstand the local stresses generated and to evaluate whether the concentration will be the adequate or not, considering its shape. Finite Element Methods (FEM) tools are used to evaluate both factors (fig. 5), which will be supported by laboratory tests carried out at the UPM facilities.

Fig 5. Finite element simulations mirror stresses its final shape

Fig 6. Considered receiver designs and the thermal model scheme

Once the concentration is known, the useful energy absorbed by the heat transfer fluid must be estimated by subtracting the energy dissipated on the receiver (fig. 6). The thermal

loss models developed at the UNED will be used for this task.

The thermal losses will be given by expressions such as equation 1 [8].

$$\dot{q}_{perd}'' = \dot{q}_{abs}'' - F'_{crit} \cdot [\dot{q}_{abs}'' - \dot{q}_{crit}'] + \dot{q}_{perd,soportes}'' \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$\dot{q}_{crit}'' = \sigma \cdot \varepsilon_{ext} \cdot (T_{fe}^4 - T_{ext}^4) + h_{ext} \cdot (T_{fe} - T_{ext}) \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$F'_{crit} = \frac{1}{\frac{U_{crit+1}}{U_{rec}}}; U_{crit} = 4 \cdot \sigma \cdot \varepsilon_{ext} \cdot T_{fe}^3 + h_{ext} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

In such a way that the outwards heat flux per unit area (\dot{q}_{perd}'') is expressed as a function of the heat absorbed per unit area (\dot{q}_{abs}''), the thermal losses in receiver supports ($\dot{q}_{perd,soportes}''$) and two characteristic parameters of each receiver

(\dot{q}_{crit}'' , F'_{crit}) defined by equations 2 and 3 [8 and 9].

Both parameters are defined as a function of the outwards heat transfer coefficients for the specific receiver (h_{ext} y ε_{ext}) and, the inlet

temperature of the fluid at the receiver (T_{fe}) and the external conditions (T_{ext}).

These analytical models will also be supported by CFD simulations to be able to obtain the accurate values for the characteristic parameters (fig. 7).

Figure 7 shows the level of detail that will be sought with these simulations in order to obtain the different heat transfer coefficients for the proposed design.

Fig 7. CFD simulation generated by the GISTER for the development of thermal models for Fresnel collectors

Fig 8. Total energy, in a hour-by-hour basis, transferred to the fluid

The objective is to obtain the total energy transmitted to the HTF over a year, which will be obtained as a result of the integration of these tools. In figure 8, it is plotted the gained thermal energy for five years, in a hour-by-hour basis, at the end user located in Corinth (Greece).

INTEGRATED SYSTEM

The subsequent integration of the receiver model with the models dedicated to the storage and other systems, both in their pseudo-steady and dynamic versions, will allow the complete analysis of the installation and a correct design of the control systems, which will contribute to optimize their behaviour.

Therefore, a large part of the success of the project will lie in the results obtained from the models, developed by UNED and other project partners, since only small adaptations at the testing facilities will be allowed.

As a result of the project, it is expected to develop an economic and sustainable alternative that is able of covering a relevant part of the heat demand for the industry at medium temperatures (150-300 °C).

The consortium and, therefore, the STER research group is facing an important challenge in order to make a relevant contribution to a sustainable future in energy terms.

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